

ASSESSMENT OF AWARENESS, KNOWLEDGE, AND ATTITUDES TOWARD OSTEOPOROSIS AND ITS PREVENTION IN THE GENERAL POPULATION OF CHHATRAPATI SAMBHAJI NAGAR (AURANGABAD)

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ABSTRACT **Introduction:** Osteoporosis, a preventable bone disease causing low bone density and fractures, remains underdiagnosed due to lack of awareness and screening, leading to severe health risks. **Objectives:** This study aimed to assess the level of awareness, knowledge, and attitudes regarding osteoporosis and its prevention in the general population. **Methodology:** A prospective, cross-sectional, questionnaire-based survey was conducted at MGM Medical College and Hospital, Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar, in February 2025, following ICH-GCP guidelines. A total of 216 participants were surveyed across different age groups. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 25, with descriptive statistics and visual representation methods. **Results:** Among 216 respondents, osteoporosis awareness varied, with 30% (17-30 years) having low awareness, 40% (31-50 years) moderately aware but inactive, and 30% (51+ years) highly aware yet 50% neglecting prevention. The 21-30 years group was most represented (55.56%), while others contributed 0.93%-16.20%. Prevention measures included 30% taking calcium/diet changes, 45% recognizing exercise benefits, 20% engaging in bone-strengthening activities, and 60% never discussing osteoporosis with a healthcare provider. **Conclusion:** The study reveals a gap between osteoporosis awareness and prevention, especially in younger and middle-aged groups. Despite higher awareness in older adults, preventive measures remain lacking. Public health efforts should focus on early education, screening, and lifestyle changes to reduce complications and improve bone health.

KEYWORDS : Osteoporosis, awareness, bone health.

INTRODUCTION:

Osteoporosis, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), is a condition in which bone mineral density (BMD) falls 2.5 standard deviations or more below the average for young, healthy women^[1]. This systemic skeletal disorder is characterized by reduced bone mass and deterioration of bone microarchitecture, leading to increased fragility and a higher risk of fractures. It is considered a prevalent chronic metabolic bone disease, comparable to diabetes and hypertension^[2,3]. Osteoporosis becomes clinically significant when fractures occur, commonly affecting the distal radius, proximal humerus, pelvis, proximal femur, and vertebral bodies^[4].

Globally, more than one-third of adult women and one in five men are expected to suffer at least one fragility fracture in their lifetime^[1]. These fractures are associated with significant morbidity, causing pain, disability, mortality, and financial burden^[5]. The risk factors for osteoporosis are classified as modifiable and non-modifiable. Non-modifiable factors include age, gender, ethnicity, family history of osteoporosis, the timing of menarche and menopause, and a history of fractures from minor trauma in first-degree relatives. Modifiable risk factors primarily involve lifestyle choices such as smoking, excessive alcohol consumption, physical inactivity, and inadequate intake of calcium and vitamin D. Postmenopausal women are particularly vulnerable to osteoporosis, leading to a specific condition known as postmenopausal osteoporosis^[5,6,7].

Osteoporosis is a major public health concern, particularly in aging populations. Awareness and knowledge about osteoporosis and its preventive measures play a crucial role in reducing its burden. This study aims to assess the level of awareness and knowledge about osteoporosis and attitude for its prevention among general population of Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar (Aurangabad).

AIM AND OBJECTIVE:

The study aimed to assess Awareness, Knowledge and attitude about Osteoporosis and its prevention in general population of Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar (Aurangabad).

The objectives included assessing the awareness and knowledge about osteoporosis in the general population, identifying gaps in knowledge regarding osteoporosis risk factors and prevention. Additionally, the study sought to assess attitudes and perceptions toward osteoporosis-related lifestyle modifications, and determine the influence of

demographic factors on osteoporosis awareness and knowledge.

Methodology:

Cross-sectional survey was carried out among the general population residing in Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar (Aurangabad) in February 2025 following permission from the Institutional Ethics Committee (MGMECRHS). The study was conducted as per the guideline of the International Conference on Harmonization – Good Clinical Practice (ICH-GCP).

Participants selected for the survey were individuals between 18 to 85 years age of either gender and of various socioeconomic backgrounds living in Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar (Aurangabad). Individuals taking prescription medicines for osteoporosis.

Following data was recorded through a validated and structured questionnaire:

- Demographic Information
- Awareness & Knowledge about Osteoporosis
- Osteoporosis and supplementation
- Risk Factors & Lifestyle Habits

For calculation of sample size for present study, Alpha = $\alpha=0.05$, Power = 0.85, medium effect size was considered = 0.50 with 50% population proportion. Using PS software sample size was found to be 208.

Total responses collected were 216.

RESULT:

The collected data was analyzed and formulated into a result and presented. After analysis of questionnaire, among 216 participants we found that osteoporosis awareness varied significantly across age groups. The highest awareness was reported in the 18–22 (80–88%), 27–30 (87.5%), and 60+ (83.3%) age groups, while comparatively lower awareness was observed in 23–26 (70.6%) and 51–60 (71.4%). Notably, although 67% of individuals aged 60+ recognized the increased risk of fractures due to osteoporosis, only 33% perceived it as a serious health issue, indicating a disconnect between knowledge and concern.

Belief in the preventability of osteoporosis was strongest among the 27–30 (75%) and 60+ (66%) groups, but significantly low among 31–40-year-olds (4.76%). Regarding supplementation, 41–50-year-

olds showed the highest recognition of the importance of calcium and vitamin D (88%), while only 25% of 23–26-year-olds acknowledged its relevance. Concern about osteoporosis followed a similar trend, being highest in 27–30 (75%) but notably lower in 23–26 (17.65%) and 51–60 (21.43%). Encouragingly, 100% of individuals in the 27–30, 51–60, and 60+ age groups expressed a willingness to adopt lifestyle changes for prevention, while younger adults showed less proactive engagement.

Figure1: Graphical representation of participants who knew about osteoporosis

Figure2: Graphical representation of participants who think osteoporosis is preventable.

Figure3: Graphical representation of participants willing to adopt lifestyle changes to prevent osteoporosis

DISCUSSION:

The results indicate that while general awareness of osteoporosis is present across age groups, it does not consistently translate into appropriate perception or preventive behaviour. The high awareness in younger and older adults contrasts with the low concern and low belief in preventability in the 23–40 age bracket, suggesting a gap between knowledge and action. This is especially concerning in the 31–40 age group, where belief in preventability was alarmingly low (4.76%), despite their being within the age range where preventive habits could significantly impact long-term bone health.

Similarly, low supplement awareness in younger adults (23–26: 25%) despite overall awareness, and underestimation of severity by 60+ individuals (only 33% considered it serious), reflect inconsistent risk perception. While older adults were more willing to adopt lifestyle changes, younger adults' passive attitudes underline the need for age-specific educational interventions. These findings align with previous studies that highlight the role of targeted messaging in improving public understanding of osteoporosis and translating awareness into meaningful action.

CONCLUSION:

Osteoporosis awareness was generally high, but significant gaps remain in risk perception, belief in preventability, and supplement use—especially among younger and middle-aged adults. The

disconnect between knowledge and action highlights the need for targeted education to promote early prevention and informed health behavior.

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